

MODEL OF IMPROVING STUDENTS' SPEECH COMPETENCE

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ABSTRACT

The article examines the scientific and practical problem of the formation and development of speech competence of students of higher educational institutions. A structural-functional model for the formation of such competence is described. The main components of this model are presented: tasks, principles, criteria, levels and stages, methods and techniques of its formation.

Introduction. To organize the training process of future English language teachers in our country based on international qualification requirements, to train future English language teachers based on advanced foreign experience, to train specialists who can communicate freely in foreign languages is the norm for the wide use of the achievements of world civilization. foundations were created and the material and technical base was enriched. In the Strategy of Actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "increasing the quality and efficiency of higher education institutions based on the introduction of international education standards and evaluation of the quality of education"[1] was set as a priority. As a result, the possibility of teaching languages integrated with subjects in higher education institutions has expanded.

The formation of speech competence is currently becoming an increasingly important condition for successful self-determination, development and self-awareness of students. Further professional activities of students will depend on the level of development of oral and written speech in the classes at the university.

The author's textbook, created to determine the speech competence of students, helps to determine the level of its development and establish a connection with the psychological characteristics of a person. In the process of its development, various research methods were used: empirical data collection (test, questionnaire, direct, indirect, participant observation, interview, conversation, experiment, measuring, summarizing the personality characteristics of students' speech, etc.); praximetric (analysis of activity products); constructive and interpretive (factor and correlation analyses, quantitative and qualitative evaluations; statistical and mathematical data processing), identification and formation experiments are used. The relevance of modeling students' speech competence is due to the need to increase the efficiency of their training, the lack of empirical material, the expediency of presenting, analyzing and summarizing the results of research activities on this problem.

Literature analysis and methods

The modeling process is based on the construction of a model that best reflects the essential features of the formation of speech competence. A reasonable definition of a model created by a person is given by V. A. Shtoff: "A model is understood as such a mentally represented or materially realized system that, by displaying or reproducing an object of study, is capable of replacing it so that its study gives us new information about this object." [2, p. 22].

Modeling as a theoretical-cognitive procedure, carried out on the basis of abstract logical thinking, is the reproduction of the characteristics of a certain object on another, specially created one, which is called a model. At their core, all models can be considered symbolic or metaphorical, and not simply reflective of reality [3]. This definition of a model includes the following features: a model is a mentally represented or materially realized system; reproduction or reflection of the research object; object replacement [4].

Analysis of scientific literature made it possible to identify and describe several types of models of speech competence. The first model can be characterized as stage-based. It is presented in the study of R. Kh. Shakurov, who considers three stages of the management process: target, socio-psychological and operational [5].

The second model is functional. It was developed by N.V. Kuzmina, who identifies five main functional components: gnostic, design, constructive, organizational and communicative. These components, reflected in the activities of a specialist, become the basis for managing the educational process. The gnostic component acts as the initial and system-forming factor, since it is associated with obtaining information about all aspects of the functioning of the system [6]. The structural-functional principle, which we take as a basis, involves the identification of certain structural components, functions and criteria for assessing speech competence, and taking into account educational situations. In the work of one of the authors of this type of modeling, B.F. Lomov, a situation is understood as the moment of interaction between the subject and circumstances [7]. To the varieties of social situations

The learning situation in the classroom can also be included.

The third model is a gaming one. According to G.P. Shchedrovitsky [8], A.A. Verbitsky [9] and other psychologists, the game is the embodiment of a systematic approach to the analysis, design and organization of social processes.

Based on the analysis of psychological and pedagogical research, we consider it possible to identify in the structure of students' speech competence a basic component necessary for the training of any specialist in the educational process of a university; a professionally oriented component, including knowledge, abilities, skills, experience of speech activity and reflection, which determine the student's speech preparation for the implementation of specific professional actions, and a personality-oriented component, which allows taking into account individual characteristics, inclinations and interests in the implementation of speech activity within the framework of specialization.

The model for the formation of a student's speech competence includes: the goal (the formation of speech competence in the educational process of the university); tasks (formation of scientific and educational interest, communicative motivation; development of value orientations in the use of speech by students; study and assimilation of the normative foundations of speech by students; involvement of students in professional activities based on the conscious use of speech, creation of contextual professional situations; formation of

reflexive abilities in relation to speech action in specific communication situations); methodological approaches (competency-based, personal-activity and contextual); principles (integrity and consistency, continuity, variability of the content of the material, the leading role of joint activities, pedagogically sound combination of innovative (problem-search, communicative, gaming, etc.) and traditional pedagogical forms, methods, techniques and teaching aids); criterion-level characteristics of students' speech competence, which includes the main directions of speech competence formation: rhetorical and psychological-pedagogical; criteria for determining the formation of levels of speech competence - motivational (communicative motivation, desire to communicate), cognitive (knowledge), activity (skills and skills), reflective (criterion of self-esteem, self-formation), value-semantic (values of cognition and communication, awareness of the value of language) and levels: intuitive-situational, functionally adequate and initiative-creative, as well as stages: stage I formation of students' speech competence with an emphasis on the basic component; stage II – formation of speech competence of future specialists with an emphasis on the professionally oriented component; stage III – formation of speech competence of students with a focus on the personality-oriented component of speech competence.

The program for developing students' speech competence contains theoretical and practical parts. The theoretical part involves studying the concept of "speech competence of students" and its components; communication as a special type of professional activity of a student, its structure and functions; psychological-pedagogical, sociolinguistic, linguistic-psychological approaches to communication.

The practical part includes: forms (problem lectures, lecture-presentations, public speaking competitions); methods ("Socratic dialogue", discussions, problem solving, abstracting, annotation, text analysis); techniques (exercises on speech technique, tasks to develop attention, the ability to listen and analyze information, warm-up exercises, etc.); tools (multimedia presentations, electronic textbooks, tables, diagrams, etc.).

Conditions ensuring the effectiveness of the process of developing student speech competence in the educational process of the university:

- systematic diagnosis of the level of development of speech competence;
- taking into account its individual level;
- dialogical style of communication between teacher and students;
- interdisciplinary and metasubject connections between psychological, pedagogical and speech science disciplines in the process of developing students' speech competence;
- inclusion of students in independent creative activity, during which they acquire knowledge, abilities and skills, experience in speech activity and reflection, which constitute speech competence;
- implementation of a program for developing speech competence.

The developed model reflects the main directions of developing a student's speech competence - rhetorical and psychological-pedagogical. To assess the level of development of speech competence, the main criteria were identified: the desire to communicate, communicative motivation (motivational), knowledge (cognitive), abilities and skills (activity), the value of cognition and communication, attitude towards the native language (value-semantic), abilities and skills analysis and self-analysis of speech activity (reflective).

These criteria were identified on the basis of the opinion of supporters of the competency-based approach in education, who in the concept of “competence”, in addition to knowledge, abilities and skills, include reflective, motivational and value-semantic components.

The linguo-psychological model for the formation of speech competence of future specialists is based on holistic and systemic approaches that reflect the unity and interaction of structural components: target, content, motivational, information-processual, emotional-volitional, control-diagnostic and criterion-evaluative.

1. The target component means that for the successful formation of a future specialist it is necessary that students clearly understand and accept the importance of achieving interrelated goals: teaching, educational and developmental.

2. The content component is related to the definition of those communication skills that are included in the curriculum for the discipline “Russian language and speech culture” and didactic material for conducting classes.

3. The motivational component is the formation of stable motives for increasing knowledge, an active attitude towards learning, professional motives, and stimulating interest in self-improvement.

4. The information-procedural component is a system of knowledge and skills in the Russian language necessary to obtain professional knowledge and develop professionally significant communicative qualities.

5. The emotional-volitional component is of great importance, since without the formation of volitional qualities (dedication, discipline, organization, perseverance, endurance, self-control, determination, etc.), it is difficult for students to realize their full potential.

The process of developing the speech competence of future specialists should be emotionally positive. This is influenced by the motivation of students, stimulating them to learn, and the use of various didactic techniques and methods that promote the development of cognitive interests and make the process of forming speech competence an exciting character. These include the use of TV technologies and Internet technologies.

6. The control and diagnostic component is a step-by-step diagnostic control of the level of development of students’ speech competence in order to identify their knowledge, skills and abilities; carrying out an analysis of the achievement of the set goals of educational and educational work, their results; promoting the development of more capable students and helping those who has learning difficulties.

7. The criterion-evaluative component consists of determining the criteria for the development of speech competence and confirming the selected criterion; in regularly checking and assessing the progress and quality of students’ knowledge, which stimulates their educational and cognitive activity (feedback); in assessing the results of educational activities.

The practice of conducting active communicative teaching of students has given the ability to classify active learning methods as follows:

1. Non-imitation forms of classes (problem lecture, workshop, group discussion, brainstorming).

2. Simulation forms of classes, which are divided into non-game (analysis of specific situations, solving situational problems, brainstorming) and game (game design, business game, training of certain professionally necessary skills).

Methods and techniques for teaching students include:

1. General interactive methods: creative tasks, work in small groups, educational games (role-playing games and simulations, business games and simulations, educational games), other extracurricular teaching methods (radio and newspapers, films, performances, exhibitions, performances).

2. Private interactive methods:

- studying and consolidating new information material (using questions, “Socratic dialogue”, etc.);
- work with documents (general recommendations, drafting documents, written work to substantiate one’s position);
- discussion of complex and controversial issues;
- problem solving (“decision tree”, “brainstorming”).

Results

The goals and place of application of various types of techniques depend on the cognitive level to which it is necessary to bring the student at a particular stage of training:

1. Level of knowledge - the student must memorize, memorize, reproduce.
2. Level of understanding - the student must explain, convey in other words.
3. Level of application - the student must use knowledge in another situation.
4. Level of analysis - the student must understand the relationship of parts to the whole, analyze the structure, cause-and-effect relationships, and note errors.
5. Level of assessment - the student must evaluate phenomena based on criteria and provide evidence.
6. Synthesis level - the student must regroup individual parts and create a new whole.

The process of communicative training of students should be gradually aimed at performing actions that involve:

- diagnostics (students should be invited to take part in discussions, simple role-playing games so that they have the opportunity to assess their own level of proficiency in basic applied communicative knowledge and skills, and the teacher could assess the degree of development of students’ practical speech skills and plan further classes);
- demonstration of skills (the goal is to show students the technology of a particular speech act in typical situations);
- demonstration of typical mistakes (the teacher (or a trained student) specifically makes one or two typical mistakes during a role-playing game; participants must recognize them and comment on the “unprofessional” speech actions of the demonstrator, suggesting ways to correct the mistakes);
- training of a separate speech skill (it is important to determine exactly which skill should be taught to students in a particular lesson);
- training of a set of speech skills (long role-playing games are most suitable for such training);
- training in observation and commenting (this goal is pursued throughout all classes, while developing the skills of constructive criticism and cooperation, which are so necessary for a future professional career);
- assessment of the effectiveness of training (this is a diagnosis of the learning process itself, checking the effectiveness of the teamwork of all participants).

Thus, optimization of work on the formation of speech competence of university students, future specialists, provides for:

- systematic diagnostics of the level of development of students' speech competence;
- taking into account the individual level of speech culture;
- establishment of interdisciplinary and metasubject connections between psychological, pedagogical and linguistic disciplines;
- inclusion of students in independent creative activities, in the process of which knowledge, abilities and skills, experience of speech activity and reflection that constitute speech competence are acquired;
- implementation of a program for the formation of speech competence;
- optimization of the content of material in linguistic disciplines by giving it a professional orientation, increasing the limit of educational time and optimally distributing it for the entire period studying at a university;
- gradual formation of speech competence of future specialists at a basic, professionally oriented, personality-oriented level;
- systematic monitoring of the development and formation of verbal communication of the future specialist during his studies at the university;
- optimization of the content of educational programs, thematic plans, methodological developments, increasing their professional focus on speech training of students, compensating for the lack of study time by imparting a communicative developmental focus to educational activities;
- development of a program for improving the speech competence of teachers, aimed at constantly and systematically increasing the level of professional and speech culture with periodic demonstration of achievements during open and demonstrative classes, during presentations at scientific and methodological seminars, university conferences.

Discussion

The teacher starts interrupting the sequence of messages with questions to the whole group. Students should answer these questions using the appropriate part of the prepared message. Soon, the students will begin to complete the messages of their classmates using the material they have prepared on their own initiative, and then start asking questions, following the example of the teacher. A series of messages gradually turns into a conversation. As the worldview of students expands, so does the content of the conversation.

Students need to move from presenting facts, events, and specific information to their own evaluations, developing their own opinions, and discussions and debates. The more serious and deeper the content of a certain issue is discussed, the more deep and sensitive language such a discussion requires. At the same time, students' interest in the content of the lesson is awakened and active acquisition of language forms is encouraged.

Conclusion

Students need to move from presenting facts, events, and specific information to their own evaluations, developing their own opinions, and discussions and debates. The more serious and deeper the content of a certain issue is discussed, the more deep and sensitive language such a discussion requires. At the same time, students' interest in the content of the lesson is awakened and active acquisition of language forms is encouraged.

Thus, teaching students professional speech competences in a foreign language is the only process of increasing students' thinking level, and it is appropriate to consider the level of development of speech competence, which is a means of communication and thinking.

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